

Convolutional Neural Networks for the Detection of Multiclass Plant Diseases

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Abstract:- Most industrialised countries' economies are based on agriculture. Crop production is one of the most influential factors in a country's domestic market scenario. Agricultural output is also a crucial component of every country's economic development. Agriculture is critical because it offers raw materials, work, and food to a diverse population. Overuse of chemical fertilisers, pollution of water supplies with chemicals, irregular rainfall patterns, shifting soil fertility, and other factors are among them. Apart from these challenges, disease-related loss of a significant section of output is one of the most prominent roadblocks across the world. The presence of illnesses in the grown plants decreases a major share of the yield after delivering efficient resources to the fields. As a result, scientists have been working on a new project. As a result, scientists are focused their efforts on developing effective ways for detecting illness in plants. Plant diseases are a major problem for small-scale farmers because they disrupt the food supply. To provide efficient processes for diagnosis and avoidance of destruction, it is necessary to identify the kind of plant disease existing as soon as possible. Significant progress has been achieved in discovering plant diseases that impact a range of crops in different regions of the world in recent years. Image capture, preprocessing, and segmentation are all steps in the process of detecting plant diseases. It's additionally enhanced by a number of feature extraction and classification methods.

Keywords:- Plant disease, VGG16, InceptionV3, Resnet50, Hybrid model.

I. INTRODUCTION

In this world, detection of plant diseases from diseased plant leaves is a significant development in agriculture. Furthermore, early and precise agricultural disease identification enhances crop output and quality. Because of the great diversity of agricultural products, even farmers and pathologists may struggle to identify plant diseases from sick leaves. However, in poor nations' rural regions, eye inspection remains the most prevalent technique of illness detection. It is also necessary to have expert monitoring. Farmers in rural places must drive long distances to meet with specialists, wasting both time and money. In finding and diagnosing plant diseases, farmers benefit from the high throughput and precision of automated computer systems. Farmers and agronomists benefit from the high throughput and precision of automated computational systems for detecting and diagnosing plant diseases. Researchers have

proposed a number of strategies to address the issues mentioned above. For the categorization of plant diseases, many types of feature sets may be employed in machine learning. Traditional methods and deep-learning-based characteristics are the most seen features among them. The most promising way for automatically learning decisive and discriminative characteristics is to use deep-learning-based algorithms, specifically CNNs. Deep learning (DL) is made up of several convolutional layers that reflect data learning characteristics. Using a deep-learning algorithm, plant diseases may be detected. Deep learning has certain disadvantages, such as the fact that it takes a lot of data to train the network. Performance suffers if the supplied dataset lacks sufficient pictures.

II. LITERATURE SURVEY

Manual procedures are used to validate and manage plant disease in the majority of cases. Unaided eye perception is one such important approach. In any event, this strategy necessitates continual observation of the region by someone with better knowledge of the plants and illnesses that affect them. Likewise, the expert must be available in a timely manner, or else it may result in loss. The presence of a disease on a plant can also be determined by research centre testing. The harvest's ability to fight back is being harmed by this manual testing procedure.

III. DEEP LEARNING ALGORITHMS

CNN Algorithm: A convolution neural network (CNN) is a specific type of artificial neural network that uses perceptrons, an AI unit computation, for supervised learning and information inquiry. CNNs are used in image preprocessing, speech processing, and a variety of other cognitive tasks. A ConvNet is a name for a convolutional neural network.

VGG16 Model: The VGG16 architecture is built on a convolutional neural network (CNN). It is widely acknowledged to be one of the most effective vision model designs to date. VGG16 is remarkable for having 3x3 filter convolution layers with a stride 1 and always using the same padding and maxpool layer of 2x2 filter stride 2. Throughout the design, the convolution and max pool layers are positioned in the same order. At last, there are two FC (completely connected layers) and a softmax layer as output. The 16 in VGG16 alludes to the fact that there are 16 layers with different weights. This network is much larger, with over lakhs (approximation) of parameters. Two additional dense layers added along the VGG16 model.

Resnet50 Model: ResNet-50 is a 50-layer deep convolutional neural network. You may use the ImageNet database to load a pretrained version of the network that has been trained on over a million photos. This network has ability to categorize various images into hundreds of different item categories, including books, birds, and a broad variety of animals. As a result, the network has picked up a variety of rich feature representations for a variety of photos. The network's picture input size is 224 by× 224 pixels. The Resnet50 model here has two more additional dense layers with Relu activation functions.

InceptionV3 Model: Inception-v3 is a 48-layer deep convolutional neural network model that has been pre-trained. It's a version of the network that's already been trained on millions of photos from the ImageNet collection. It's the third iteration of Google's Inception CNN model, which was first proposed during the ImageNet Recognition Challenge. Convolutional Neural Networks employ Inception Modules to provide more efficient computation and deeper networks by reducing dimensionality using stacked 11 convolutions. Two additional dense layers added along the InceptionV3 model.

Layers of CNN are:

- **Convolution Layer-** CNNs are a type of Neural Network that has shown to be incredibly effective in a variety of situations. Recognize and classify images, for example. CNNs are multilayered feed-forward neural networks. CNNs are made up of filters, kernels, or neurons with learnable loads, inclinations, and parameters. Each filter takes a few input components, convolutions them, and alternates between them.
- **Pooling Layer-** The pooling layer reduces the complexity of each activation map while maintaining the most important information. The images are divided into a large number of non-covering square forms. A non-linear procedure, such as average or maximum, is used to check each zone. This layer, which is frequently placed between convolutional layers, achieves superior speculation, faster assembly, and is powerful to interpretation and distortion.
- **Activation Layer-** The activation layer regulates how signals flow from one layer to the next, simulating how neurons in our brain are terminated. More neurons would be activated by output signals that are strongly linked to previous references, allowing indications to propagate more effectively for identification. CNN is equipped with a wide range of complicated enactment capacities for demonstrating signal propagation, the most basic of which is the Rectified linear measure (ReLU), which is favoured for its faster processing speed.
- **Fully Connected-** The system's last levels are fully connected, meaning that neurons from previous layers are linked to neurons in subsequent layers. This is similar to high-level thinking, in which every possible path from input to output is considered.
- **Loss -** During the training of the neural network, there is an additional layer known as the misfortune layer. This layer assesses the neural network's ability to distinguish

information sources and, if not, the accuracy of its estimations. Because it trains, this aids in directing the neurological system to reinforce the proper beliefs. During training, this is always the final layer.

IV. ATTRIBUTES AND DATASET

This dataset was reconstructed from the original dataset using offline augmentation. This github project contains the original dataset. This collection contains around 87,500 rgb photos of healthy and sick crop leaves, which are divided into 38 classifications. The complete dataset is divided into an 80/20 training and validation set, with the directory structure preserved.

V. CONCLUSION

The use of monitoring checking and executive frameworks is rising in demand with the advancement of technology, according to this article. In the world of gardening. The majority of crop loss occurs as a result of a long distance, the spread of illness The model's accuracy is 87.47 percent. We have compared three different models of CNN models in which two dense layers are added to each VGG16, ResNet50, and InceptionV3 models and found that VGG16 models provides higher accuracy and hence leads to find better CNN model for plant diseases detection.

Future works in the project can be done by developing a hybrid model which can further provide much higher accuracy. AutoML can be employed which will provide more accuracy.

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[0.8747412, 0.29821146, 0.43387318]
Maximum accuracy for the vgg16 model with 87.47411966323853
Testing with VGG16
The confidence for the prediction is : 45.92159390449524
Tomato__Bacterial_spot
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Fig. 1

Fig. 2

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